

PROVING THE SOLUTION OF DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS WITH LINEAR OPERATOR COEFFICIENTS THROUGH THEOREMS

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Abstract: As we know, the science of partial differentials is an integral part of our life. They can be divided into two types. These are called correct and incorrect questions. In this topic, we will mainly work on the equation of heat distribution and talk about its incorrectly set problems.

Key words: heat diffusion equation, differential equation, operator, function, complex differentiation.

Suppose that $u(t)$ is a function of a scalar argument t and takes its values from the Gilbert space U , and let $u(t)$ is a function of a scalar argument t and takes its values from a Gilbert space F , A is a linear operator mapping from U to F .

$$\frac{du}{dt} = Au + f \quad (1.1)$$

This we call differential equations with operator-type coefficients.

Theorem 1.1 Let U and F be real Gilbert spaces in equation (1.2), and let A be a self-adjoint operator. Then the following inequality holds

$$\|u(t)\| \leq \|u(T)\|^{t/T} \|u(0)\|^{(T-t)/T}. \quad (1.4)$$

Proof. Assume that $u(t) \neq 0$ for all $t \in [0, T]$, and let the function $u(t)$ be twice continuously differentiable. This

$$\varphi(t) = \|u(t)\|^2 = (u, u), \quad \psi(t) = \ln \varphi(t)$$

let's look at the functions. By differentiating the function $\varphi(t)$, taking into account equation (1.2), we find after integration by pieces

$$\varphi'(t) = 2(u, u_t) = 2(u, Au)$$

$$\varphi''(t) = 2(u_t, u_t) + 2(u, A^2u) = 4(Au, Au)$$

Now we differentiate the function $\psi(t)$ twice and

Taking into account the Cauchy-Buniakovsky inequality, we form

$$\psi''(t) = \frac{\varphi(t)\varphi''(t) - (\varphi'(t))^2}{\varphi^2(t)} \geq 0.$$

The last inequality shows that the function $\psi(t)$ is concave, so

$$\psi(t) \leq \frac{t}{T}\psi(0) + \frac{T-t}{T}\psi(T)$$

will be appropriate. This leads to inequality (1.4).

Now the function $u(t)$ does not have a derivative of the second order we will look. This function depends on the parameter h

$$g_h(t) = \frac{1 + \cos \frac{\pi t}{h}}{2h}$$

let's look. This function is smooth enough that

$$g_h(-h) = g_h(h), \quad \int_{-h}^h g_h(t)dt = 1$$

satisfies the conditions. Using this function, the following

$$u_h(t) = \int_{t-h}^{t+h} g_h(\tau)d\tau$$

we construct the function. We have here a concrete function $g_h(t)$,

in general, the function $g_h(t)$ can be a sufficiently smooth function that satisfies the above conditions. The function $g_h(t)$ is twice continuously differentiable and is the solution of the equation (1.2) on the section $[h, T-h]$.

Optional from the above considerations t_1, t_2, t ($h \leq t_1 \leq t \leq t_2 \leq T - h, t_1 < t_2$) lar $\psi_h(t) = \ln \|u_h(t)\|$ for the function $\psi_h''(t) \geq 0$ or the following inequality holds

$$\|u_h(t)\| \leq \|u_h(t_2)\|^{\frac{t-t_1}{t_2-t_1}} \|u_h(t_1)\|^{\frac{t_2-t}{t_2-t_1}}. \quad (1.5)$$

it turns out to be. In the last inequality, passing to the limit $h \rightarrow 0$, we have proved that inequality (1.2) holds for the function $u(t)$ in this case as well.

If the function $u(t)$ is equal to zero for some $t_0 \in [0, T]$, then it follows from inequality (1.4) that $u(t)$ is for any arbitrary $t_0 \in [0, T]$. The theorem is proved.

Result 1.1 The solution of the Cauchy problem for equation (1.2) is unique.

Theorem 1.2 For the Cauchy problem for equation (16.2) to be correct, it is necessary and sufficient that the operator A is semi-bounded from above.

Proof. Suppose that A is a family of projection operators corresponding to operator $\{E_\lambda\}$:

$$A = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \lambda dE_\lambda$$

If A is semibounded from the operator field, then

$$A = \int_{-\infty}^a \lambda dE_\lambda$$

The solution of the Cauchy problem inserted into the equation (1.2) takes this form

$$u(t) = \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \exp(\lambda t) dE_\lambda \right) u_0, \quad u(0) = u_0.$$

This is true, because it was proved above that the solution of this problem is unique, and this function satisfies the equation and the initial condition. It is not difficult to see that the solution is a continuous dependence on the givens.

Now let the operator A be semi-bounded from above. Then, for arbitrary $a > 0$, we find $b > a$ such that

$U_{ab} = (E_a - E_b)U$ part space is not empty.

Suppose $u_0 \in U_{ab}$. Then the norm of the solution of the Cauchy problem (corresponding to u_0) satisfies this inequality

$$\|u(t)\| = \left\| \int_a^b e^{\lambda t} dE u_0 \right\| \geq e^{at} \|u_0\|. \quad (1.6)$$

It can be seen from (1.6) that sufficiently small Cauchy givens by norm can

correspond to sufficiently large solutions by norm, that is, the solution does not have a continuous dependence on givens. The theorem is proved.

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